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THE EFFECT OF A LISTENING PROCESS-BASED MODEL ON IMPROVING LISTENING COMPREHENSION SKILLS AMONG TENTH-GRADE FEMALE STUDENTS

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ABSTRACT

The study aimed to reveal the effect of using the listening process stages model in developing listening comprehension skills among tenth- grade female students, to achieve the study objectives, a listening comprehension skills was developed, the test consists of (25) items distributed across the following skills: the skill of remembering what was heard, the skill of understanding and analyzing the spoken text, and the skill of appreciating and critiquing what was heard. The study followed the quasi-experimental method. The study group consisted of (40) female students from the tenth grade of basic education, who were divided into two groups. The study results showed a significant improvement in the level of listening comprehension skills among the experimental group in the post-test, with a high effect size of (0.675). The study also confirms the effectiveness of the listening process stages model in creating a stimulating learning environment in teaching Arabic, specifically listening skills. The study recommended employing a listening comprehension process stages model when teaching listening comprehension skills, in order to ensure the organization of the learning process and the students' progression through different levels of understanding in an organized manner.

KEYWORDS: Arabic language, listening comprehension skills, Listening process stages model, Tenth-Grade Female Students, Female Education, Language Pedagogy, Listening Strategies, Arabic Teaching.

1. INTRODUCTION

Listening comprehension is a fundamental pillar in building language proficiency. However, educational reports indicate significant challenges in acquiring this skill. UNESCO data (2024) reveals notable gaps in listening comprehension skills among learners globally. Locally, the National Report on the Reading and Numeracy Initiative in Jordan (2023) revealed a low average student performance in listening comprehension tests, reaching only 56.9%, reflecting a persistent gap between the goals of the national curriculum and actual results (Ministry of Education, 2023).

Listening skills stand out as a fundamental skill that develops qualitatively with the progression of educational stages. Proper training of students in listening skills makes them good listeners and readers, which helps them acquire other language skills and progress in different subjects. The listening process is essentially based on two basic processes: decoding phonetic symbols and understanding the connotations and meanings behind those symbols (Abu Saleh, 2017).

Listening skills receive significant attention in the Arabic language curriculum, as evidenced by the variety of language activities offered to students, primarily listening comprehension. This activity is a core component of the curriculum, aiming to enable students to understand and analyze auditory material. It relies on their auditory abilities and employs conscious listening skills to transform auditory stimuli into comprehensible meanings and connotations, thereby enriching their vocabulary, refining their auditory sense, and developing their listening skills (Jilali & Ben Zahaf, 2017).

Listening comprehension is the ultimate goal and the cornerstone of language acquisition and the development of other expressive skills. A listener who succeeds in comprehending and processing auditory input becomes more capable of employing it in speaking and writing skills (Ross, 2006). Listening comprehension skills are defined as: "Inferring the main idea from an audio story, deducing specific information after listening, guessing the meanings of unfamiliar words from the context of the audio text, and being able to predict events from the context" (Gilakjani & Ahmadi, 2011, p. 66).

Educators emphasize that understanding what is heard is a complex constructive mental process that goes through three procedural stages, beginning with reception, then selective attention to important stimuli, and finally giving meaning to the heard material (Ashour and Miqdadi, 2005). This process

requires mental effort that necessitates the learner's positive interaction with the audio text within its cultural context, and linking the new outputs to their previous experiences and knowledge (Al-Khuwaiski, 2008).

Auditory comprehension is a highly important active mental process, enabling learners to build their cognitive abilities by engaging in educational activities that integrate new learning with prior knowledge. In this way, the listener transforms from a passive recipient of information into a constructor of meaning, utilizing their prior experiences to interpret new auditory stimuli and comprehensively develop their language skills (Al Bloushi, 2024).

In light of modern trends, developing listening comprehension skills is a crucial factor in holistic language development. It contributes to enhancing students' linguistic intelligence and refining their personality and thinking. Listening comprehension is the fundamental gateway to developing critical thinking skills and connecting learners to contemporary technological and ethical issues (Fujii et al., 2026). This makes listening a tool for grasping abstract ideas and acquiring sophisticated linguistic patterns that enable learners to address modern problems in a mature, scientific, and systematic manner (National Center for Curriculum Development, 2025). To achieve this comprehension effectively, educators believe it is necessary to frame this process within organized stages, as illustrated by the listening process model. This model outlines the learner's cognitive path through six successive stages: listening, attention, comprehension, recall, evaluation, and finally, response. It begins with listening as an innate physiological process in which the ear receives sound vibrations, often without conscious effort (Nunan, 2001).

In the field of Arabic language teaching and learning, procedural models for structured listening are a cornerstone for developing listening comprehension skills. These models enable learners to process audio material through progressive cognitive levels, starting with comprehension and recall, and progressing to appreciation and critical analysis. A study by Hocaoglu and Ocak (2024) indicated that teaching listening strategies effectively contributed to developing students' listening comprehension and speaking skills, raising their awareness of how to listen, and increasing their motivation to learn the language.

The study by Palanisamy and Rajasekaran (2025) emphasized the importance of targeted interventions to enhance listening comprehension skills in education, based on listening strategies. Qualitative

data from the study by Robilos and Bustos (2022) confirmed students' acceptance of interventions based on listening strategies and the development of positive views regarding the role of these strategies in the success of the listening process.

The study by Sakurai and Spring (2026) demonstrated a positive correlation between the quality of note-taking organization and the ability to extract main ideas, as well as the efficiency of listening comprehension. Furthermore, the results of the study by Al-Sulaiti et al. (2025) revealed positive student attitudes toward using this strategy to develop listening comprehension skills.

Despite the value of previous studies, it is noticeable that most of them addressed listening skills in a fragmented manner, failing to integrate the sequential procedural stages (reception, comprehension, recall, analysis, and appreciation) into a comprehensive mental model that explains how students process spoken text from the initial moment until they reach an aesthetic judgment. Furthermore, a number of these studies focused on literal or inferential comprehension without directly addressing the skill of appreciating spoken language at its affective and critical levels among upper elementary students. The research gap that this study seeks to fill is the scarcity of studies that have examined the listening process stages model as a procedural framework that combines reception, comprehension, recall, analysis, and appreciation simultaneously.

Based on the above, and given the importance of listening comprehension, this study aims to investigate the impact of the listening process stages model on improving listening comprehension skills among tenth-grade female students. It seeks to answer the following main question: "What is the impact of using the listening process stages model on developing listening comprehension skills among tenth-grade female students in Jordan?"

2. METHODOLOGY

2.1 Research Design

The study followed a quasi-experimental design to determine the effectiveness of employing the listening process stages model during Arabic language teaching in developing listening comprehension skills among tenth-grade female students.

The design included two groups: a control group and an experimental group. A completely randomized experimental design was not possible due to institutional constraints, especially the inability to randomly assign participants between the

two study groups. Instead, a pre-test and post-test methodology was used within the study population, allowing for comparison between the two study groups.

2.2. Participants and Context

The study participants consisted of 40 tenth-grade female students, selected purposively due to the researcher's employment at the school. This facilitated the study's implementation and ensured continuous monitoring, as the researcher supervised its execution within the school. Existing classes were chosen to form the two study groups, each comprising 20 students. One group served as the experimental group, taught using the listening process stages model, while the other served as the control group, taught using the traditional method. The participants' ages ranged from 15 to 16 years, and they came from relatively homogeneous social, cultural, and educational backgrounds. Although the convenience sampling method inherently limits the generalizability of the results due to the potential for sample bias, the relative homogeneity of the sample enhanced internal consistency and reduced the influence of external variables. This type of concentration sampling is often considered suitable for exploratory research aimed at studying specific phenomena within specific contexts.

2.3. Instrumentation

To achieve the study's objectives, the researcher developed an auditory comprehension skills test. This test aimed to provide a measurement tool with an acceptable degree of validity and reliability, suitable for the characteristics and developmental level of tenth-grade students. The test was designed to measure three main skills: auditory recall, auditory comprehension and analysis, and auditory appreciation and critique. The test consisted of three audio texts, each accompanied by a set of questions. The test comprised 25 multiple-choice items, distributed across the three skills to ensure a balanced assessment of each.

The initial version of the test was presented to a group of experienced and specialized judges, and their comments were taken into consideration, and the necessary modifications were made. In order to verify the construct validity of the listening comprehension test, it was administered to a pilot sample of 20 female students, and Pearson's correlation coefficients were calculated between each item and the skill to which it belonged, and between each skill and the total test score, to verify internal consistency and construct validity. The correlation

coefficients between the items of the listening comprehension test and the total test score were within statistically significant and acceptable values, ranging between (0.36–0.81) for the listening recall skill, between (0.23–0.79) for the listening text comprehension and analysis skill, and between (0.33–0.90) for the listening appreciation and critique skill. All of these reflect good internal consistency between the test items and the instrument as a whole. The correlation coefficients between the items and the skill level to which they belong ranged between (0.34–0.94), indicating the validity of each item in measuring its own skill. The value of the correlation coefficient (0.20) was adopted as a criterion for accepting items, as indicated by Gay & Mills (2016).

The scale was administered again to the same sample two weeks later to calculate the correlation coefficient between the two administrations (retest reliability). The test-retest reliability coefficients ranged from 0.72 to 0.80 for the subdomains and reached 0.88 for the test as a whole, all of which were higher than 0.70, indicating the scale's reliability. The internal consistency reliability coefficients (Cronbach's alpha) for the subdomains ranged from 0.77 to 0.89, while the reliability coefficient for the test as a whole reached 0.92. These high values indicate the homogeneity of the instrument's items and its good internal consistency (Nunnally & Bernstein, 1994).

The difficulty indices for the listening comprehension test items were calculated and ranged from 0.50 to 0.85, falling within the statistically acceptable range of 0.30 to 0.80. This indicates that the listening comprehension test items are of an appropriate level of difficulty, with no items being too easy or too difficult. Discrimination indices ranged from 0.35 to 0.78, with the majority of items achieving acceptable discrimination indices (0.20 or higher). This reflects the test items' overall good ability to differentiate between high-achieving and low-achieving students (Gay & Mills, 2016).

2.4. Procedure

For the purposes of conducting the study, the study followed these procedures:

- Review the theoretical literature and previous studies related to the study variables to develop the research instrument and ensure its validity and reliability.
- Ensure the equivalence of the two study groups (control and experimental) in their pre-test performance of listening comprehension skills using the independent samples t-test, as shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Results of the t-test to determine the equivalence of the two study groups in the pre-test performance of the listening comprehension test.

Dependent variable	group	Mean	SD	t-test	sig.
The skill of remembering what is heard	Control	4.25	0.64	-0.857	0
	Experimental	4.45	0.83		
The skill of understanding and analyzing text	Control	3.60	0.68	0.370	0
	Experimental	3.50	1.00		
The skill of appreciating and critiquing heard	Control	2.05	0.51	-0.686	0
	Experimental	2.20	0.83		
Auditory Comprehension Test as a Whole	Control	9.90	1.17	-0.581	0
	Experimental	10.15	1.53		

Table 1 shows that there is no statistically significant difference between the average performance of the two study groups for the listening comprehension and skills test; this indicates that the two groups were statistically equivalent before the treatment

- Administer the research instrument to the study participants beforehand.
- Train a teacher on the listening process stages model, and then teach both groups, using the listening process stages model for the experimental group and the traditional method for the control group.
- Administer the research instrument afterward.
- Extract and discuss the results, and present the main recommendations.

2.5. Data Analysis

The means and standard deviations of the students' scores on the listening comprehension test (pre- and post-tests) were calculated to describe the performance of the participants in the experimental and control groups. The Independent Samples t-test was used to verify the equivalence of the two groups (experimental and control) in the pre-test. One-way analysis of covariance (ANCOVA) was used to detect differences between the two groups in the post-test, after controlling for the effect of the pre-test. Additionally, multivariate analysis of covariance (MANCOVA) was used to examine the effect of the listening process stages model on listening comprehension skills, again after controlling for the effect of the pre-test. The effect size was determined according to the criteria outlined by Cohen (1988), as shown in Table 2.

Table 2. Statistical criteria used to determine the level of the explained ratio and the effect size of the method.

eta (η ²)	Effect size (d)	Level of the explained and effect size
Less than 0.06	0.20 - 0.49	Low
0.06 - less than 0.1	0.50-0.79	Medium
0.16 or higher	0.80 or higher	High

3. RESULTS

To answer the research question, the means and standard deviations of the scores of the experimental and control groups on the listening comprehension skills test and its sub-skills were calculated. This was done in preparation for testing the significance of the differences between them. Table 3 shows the results:

Table 3. Means, Standard Deviations, Standard Error, and Adjusted Mean for the Post-Test Performance of the Experimental and Control Groups on the Listening Comprehension Skills Test and its Sub-Skills.

The group	Skill	pre		Post		Adjusted arithmetic mean	Standard error
		Mean	SD	Mean	SD		
Control	Remember the audible	4.25	0.6	7.05	0.287	6.60	0.16
	Understanding and analyzing spoken text	3.60	0.6	6.60	0.282	6.60	0.20
	Savouring and critiquing that is heard	2.05	0.5	4.10	0.155	4.11	0.13
	The test as a whole	9.90	1	17.75	0.41	17.81	0.30
Experimental	Remember the audible	4.45	0.8	8.60	0.14	7.80	0.16
	Understanding and analyzing spoken text	3.50	0	7.80	0.62	8.59	0.20
	Savouring and critiquing that is heard	2.20	0.8	5.20	0.170	5.19	0.13
	The test as a whole	10.15	0.5	21.60	0.154	21.54	0.30

Table 3 shows apparent differences between the mean scores of the study sample on listening comprehension skills in the experimental and control groups. To reveal the significance of the differences between these means, the analysis of covariance (ANCOVA) method was used for the post-test measurement of listening comprehension among tenth- grade students, after removing the effect of the pre-test (pre-test listening comprehension score) as a covariate to eliminate any effect of prior variance, no matter how significant, on the study results, and attributing it to the independent variable (strategy). Therefore, the statistical control provided by the one-way ANCOVA method was used. The

following is a presentation of these results, and Table (4) shows the results of this analysis.

Table 4. Results of the Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) of the study sample's scores on the post-test of listening comprehension as a whole.

Source of Variance	SS	df	Mean Sq	F value	Sig.	Partial η ²
Pre-test (accompanying)	16.1	1	16.14	8.993	0.003	0.4
Teaching Method	137.9	1	137.92	76.846	0.000	1.4
Error	66.4	37	1.793			
Total	230.4	39				

Table 4 shows that the F-value for the overall listening comprehension scale was (76.846), which is statistically significant at the significance level (α = 0.05). This indicates a statistically significant difference between the post-test scores of the two groups. Upon reviewing the arithmetic mean, the differences were found to favor the experimental group.

To determine the effect size of the listening process stages model strategy on overall listening comprehension, eta-squared was calculated and found to be (0.675). This means that approximately (67.5%) of the variance in the performance of the study participants on the post-test of listening comprehension is attributable to the listening process stages model. Therefore, the effect size is high, as indicated by Cohen (1988).

A multivariate analysis of covariance (MANCOVA) was also performed on the post-test arithmetic means of the scores of the study sample on the post-test auditory comprehension, considering the pre-test scores as a covariate. Table (5) shows the results of this analysis.

Table 5. Results of the Multivariate Covariance Analysis of Dependent Variables (MANCOVA), on the post-test arithmetic means of the study sample's scores on listening comprehension test skills.

Source	Skill	SS	df	MS	F value	Sig.	Partial η ²	Cohen's d
Pre-measurement	Remember the audible	2.624	1	2.624	1.402	0.261	0.34	0.39
	Understanding and analyzing spoken text	27.900	1	27.900	6.940	0.005	1.13	1.03
	Savouring and critiquing that is heard	2.939	1	2.939	1.743	0.062	0.20	0.50
Group F=27.052 Sig=0.000	Remember the audible	4.073	1	4.073	3.977	0.045	0.31	0.91
	Understanding and analyzing spoken text	7.437	1	7.437	3.087	0.039	0.81	0.81
	Savouring and critiquing that is heard	1.133	1	1.133	1.124	0.048	0.29	0.97

Error	remember the audible	16.997	35	0.486				
	understanding and analysing spoken text	26.435	35	0.755				
	valouring and critiquing what is heard	11.764	35	0.336				
Total	remember the audible	34.400	39					
	understanding and analysing spoken text	79.775	39					
	valouring and critiquing what is heard	27.100	39					

Table 5 shows that there are statistically significant differences in the sub-skills of the listening comprehension test, which are:

- Auditory recall skill: The F-value (28.977) was statistically significant at the significance level ($\alpha = 0.05$), with a significance level of (0.000), indicating a higher level of auditory recall skill in favor of the experimental group. Furthermore, the partial eta-squared value was (0.453), meaning that the use of the listening process stages model in teaching explained (45.3%) of the variance between the experimental and control groups in auditory recall skill scores, thus demonstrating a large effect size.
- The skill of understanding and analyzing spoken text: The F-value (23.087) was statistically significant at the significance level ($\alpha = 0.05$), with a significance level of (0.000), indicating a higher level of spoken text comprehension and analysis skills in favor of the experimental group. The partial eta-squared value was (0.397), meaning that using the listening process stages model in teaching explained (39.7%) of the variance between the experimental and control groups in scores on spoken text comprehension and analysis skills; therefore, the effect size is large.
- Auditory Appreciation and Criticism Skills: The F-value (33.124) was statistically significant at the significance level ($\alpha = 0.05$), with a significance level of (0.000), indicating a higher level of auditory appreciation and critical thinking skills in favor of the experimental group. Furthermore, the partial eta-squared value was (0.486), meaning that using the listening process stages model in teaching explained (48.6%) of the variance between the experimental and control groups in auditory appreciation and critical thinking skills scores. Therefore, the effect size is also

high.

4. DISCUSSION

The high impact of the model, according to the study results, can be explained by the nature of the model based on the phased organization of the listening process. The student goes through a series of progressive stages that begin with mental preparation, then general listening, then detailed listening, then analytical listening, reaching precise listening that includes understanding, analysis, interpretation of meaning, evaluation of what is heard and its integration with prior knowledge, then moving on to the post-listening stage. This sequence can provide an opportunity to process the heard text gradually, and provide multiple opportunities to reconstruct meaning, which leads to a deeper understanding.

The high impact is also attributed to the fact that the listening process stages model contributed to raising the efficiency of the students' cognitive interaction with the audio text, by transforming listening from an activity that depends on instantaneous understanding to an extended process that includes reorganizing and interpreting information. The listening process stages model also enhanced the students' ability to control their attention while listening, and to move consciously between different levels of understanding, which led to improved accuracy of comprehension and reduced loss of information or forgetting.

This result can also be attributed to the fact that the model integrates two processing patterns: top-down understanding through expectations or predictions and activating prior knowledge, and bottom-up understanding through focusing on linguistic and semantic details, which contributes to forming an integrated understanding of the audio text, and prevents the student from falling into partial or superficial understanding without delving into the audio information or benefiting from it.

This effect can be explained in light of information processing theory, as organizing listening and multiple opportunities to be exposed to the text led to improved attention, encoding and retrieval processes, which is reflected in the accuracy and stability of understanding. The model also contributed to enabling students to move between different levels of understanding consciously, which is consistent with the constructivist approach that emphasizes the active role of the learner in constructing meaning independently.

This result is consistent with the findings of Al-Sulaiti and others (2025) and Al-Shara'a (2025), which

showed that strategies based on step-by-step guidance and interaction contribute to improving auditory comprehension skills. It is also consistent with the study of Al-Khaza'la and others (2022), which confirmed that organizing the learning process leads to a high effect on different levels of comprehension.

This effect is also attributed to the fact that the model provided opportunities for the diversity of response patterns among students, such as interpretation and linking content to experiences, which is what the study by Al-Mousa and others (2023) indicated regarding the importance of interactive activities in developing deep understanding. In contrast, the results of the study by Mahmoud and others (2023) support this interpretation, as they showed that the weakness of listening skills may persist in the absence of organized teaching strategies, which confirms the importance of the model used in this study.

This result can also be explained by the interactive nature of the learning approach facilitated by the model used. Students transitioned from individual to collaborative or group learning based on dialogue and the exchange of viewpoints, which contributed to a deeper understanding and broader perspectives on the spoken text. Classroom discussions, open-ended questions, and listening to peers' opinions all enhanced the students' ability to form more mature critical judgments. This aligns with the findings of Hocaoglu & Ocak (2024), who indicated that teaching listening strategies in an interactive environment contributes to increased comprehension and motivation. It also supports the findings of Palanisamy & Rajasekaran (2025), who emphasized the importance of adopting critical thinking strategies in developing listening comprehension.

This result is explained in light of what Al-Omar et al (2021) indicated, that the skills of appreciation and criticism depend on conscious listening based on interaction with the text, and distinguishing its strengths and weaknesses. This requires providing educational situations that allow for dialogue, comparison, evaluation, and judgment. This model facilitated this through dialogue and evaluation activities that enhanced the ability of tenth-grade students to build understandable critical positions.

This interpretation of the result aligns with Zaitoun's (2022) assertion that appreciation represents the pinnacle of cognitive and emotional

processing of auditory information, where understanding is integrated with emotional engagement. This makes its development contingent upon the availability of deep and structured learning experiences. From this perspective, the students' progression through the three stages of listening (before, during, and after listening) contributed to the gradual development of this advanced level of understanding. It was established in the pre-listening and during-listening stages and then manifested more clearly in the post-listening stage through various critical activities.

5. CONCLUSIONS

Based on the study's findings and statistical significance, the importance of employing this model in developing the educational process is highlighted. Accordingly, the study offers several recommendations, most notably: employing the listening process stages model when teaching listening comprehension skills, ensuring the organization of the learning process and students' logical and systematic progression through different levels of understanding; training Arabic language teachers to design diverse listening activities that consider the pre-listening, listening, and post-listening stages, and enhance student engagement with meaning—a challenge this study addressed; and incorporating analytical and critical tasks into classroom activities, enabling students to engage deeply with the audio, express their opinions constructively, and foster classroom interaction through dialogue and discussion strategies, thus contributing to a comprehensive understanding of the audio content.

In light of the findings of this study, several future research projects can be suggested to broaden the scope of research in developing listening comprehension skills. These include: conducting similar studies to investigate the impact of the listening process stages model on the development of other language skills, such as speaking, reading, or writing, to determine the extent to which the model's effects transfer to different language domains; and conducting studies comparing the listening process stages model with other teaching strategies for developing listening comprehension skills, such as the (DLTA) strategy or modern interactive strategies.

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